

Original Research Article

Development of Experiential-Based Learning Model for Writing Text of Exemplum

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ABSTRACT

This research is a development research using 4-D development model aims to know the process of developing experiential learning model for writing exemplum text in grade IX students of SMP Muhammadiyah 57 Medan and whether the experiential-based learning model can improve the ability to write text exemplum on students of class IX SMP Muhammadiyah 57 Medan. The 4-D development model was developed by Thiagrajan and Sammel consisting of four stages: Define, Design, Develop, and Disseminate. In this research the development of experiential based learning model at the stage of its dissemination is done limited in SMP Muhammadiyah 57 Medan School through some validation from the validator. Subjects in this study were students of class IX-1, IX-2 and IX-3 SMP Muhammadiyah 57 Medan with limited trials and extended from small groups to large groups. Instruments used to collect data are questionnaires, interviews, student activity observation sheets and tests. Data collection tool is in the form of questionnaire using Likert scale. The data obtained were analyzed by qualitative descriptive statistic. The result of this research is that the quality of learning design from colleagues is 66,79% in the range of score $55\% \leq X \leq 75\%$ with good criterion. For the student's motivation obtained a score of 80.39% with very good criteria. Student activity during the learning process can be seen in the form of tables and graphs presented. Thus, it can be concluded that this development is suitable to be used as one of the learning strategies in the classroom.

Keywords: development, experiential learning, text extracts

INTRODUCTION

The 2013 curriculum puts Indonesian as an advocate of other subjects and therefore must be in front of all other subjects. Indonesian language learning for SMP / MTS class IX presented text-based implemented by applying the principle that the language is seen as text, not merely a collection of words or linguistic rules, the use of language is the process of selecting linguistic forms to express the meaning, language is also a means of shaping the ability of human thinking. With respect to

these principles it can be realized that within each text there is a separate structure that is different from one another. From these structures students can then process their knowledge through the ability to observe, question, associate, analyze, and present the results of the analysis adequately.

One of the text-based subject matter taught by the teacher to the students in the Indonesian language class IX is the text of the exemplum. The text of exemplum is a text that tells the character or the actor (in the Ministry of Education and Culture of the

Republic of Indonesia, 2015).^[1] In text of exemplum there is a text structure, the structure includes orientation, incident, and interpretation. This exemplum text includes the story genre and is very important to teach the teacher to the students. Because, through this text of exemplum, students can learn science in the form of messages in the text of the story he studied. In the learning material of this exemplum text, students are also invited to study more deeply about the characteristics, structure, and language features of the text of the exemplum.

Ability to write text exemplum on students of SMP Muhammadiyah 57 Medan in class IX still categorized as less satisfactory or not maximal. The statement is in line with research that has been done by Anis,^[2] which states that in learning text exemplum there are still many students who do not complete the value of its minimal mastery criteria (KKM). Other data obtained from interviews with colleagues was done to obtain data about the ability of students in writing text exemplum. The results of interviews with teachers obtained input that the text material exemplum only understood students in theory only, because the structure of the text that must be mastered by students is too difficult. In addition to learning in the classroom, teachers have difficulty in providing examples that match the problems faced by students in their daily lives. According to the teacher, based on the learning outcomes so far that can be seen from the value of previous exemplum text material lessons, the ability to write the text of the students exemplum is in the low category with a value of 60.

The results of interviews and observations conducted on class IX students of SMP Muhammadiyah 57 Medan, obstacles in learning text of exemplum include (1) lack of enthusiasm of learners in learning, (2) mastery of material exemplum text that has not been maximized, (3) assumption participants (4) Learning model used by teachers in learning to write text exemplum less effective and less in

accordance with the conditions, needs and character of students.

The cause of less enthusiastic learners in learning, especially on writing material exemplum text because the learning models used by teachers in Indonesian subjects have not been able to provide conceptual knowledge optimally. The strategies and models used have not generated the interest of students to better understand the material of the exemplum text. The statement is in line with research that has been done by Atikah^[3] which states that there are still many teachers who carry out the learning with only oriented convey knowledge to students.

In terms of teacher factors, teachers tend to use the same learning methods repeatedly for all subject matter, lecture, practice, question and answer, assignment, and teacher method only using textbooks or LKS that have been created by an agency in the lesson the desire to develop their own learning model.^[4]

Learning model used less effective and less appropriate with condition, requirement and character of student. So it takes the appropriate learning model in delivering the text material exemplum to students, so that the competencies that must be met students can be achieved well. Experiential-based learning models are expected to enable an active learning environment. The statement is supported by previous researchers conducted by Mutmainah^[5] which states that students are less given examples of applications and material benefits, so that mathematical material is ultimately absorbed only by students abstractly. The teacher should be able to enliven the learning atmosphere, so that students are not just silent as listeners only. Then the teacher is considered very necessary to apply practical learning model, interesting, fun, and meaningful in learning basic competence to write text exemplum.

Based on the above problems, the researcher took the initiative to develop an experiential learning model for writing exemplum text material to make students

more easily write text exemplum. Learning model that will be developed is one of the model of learning Student Centered Oriented that is experiential based learning model. This is in accordance with research conducted by Musdalifah, et al. ^[6]

LITERATURE REVIEW

Experiential Based Learning Model

Experiential-based learning model (learning experiential) is a learning process, a change process that uses experiential as a medium of learning or learning. Experiential-based learning model is learning which is done through reflection and also through a process of making meaning from direct experiential.

Silberman, ^[7] experiential learning is "the involvement of learners in concrete activities that enable them to 'experiential' what they are learning. This learning is based on real work / life experience and structured experience that simulate or approach actual work / life experience. "Sanjaya, ^[8] defines" the learning experiential are a number of student activities performed to obtain information and "According to Sani, ^[9] "experiential-based learning is inductive, student-centered, and activity-oriented".

Based on some of the above explanations, it can be concluded that experiential learning is a student-centered learning model based on the idea that people learn best from experiential directly. Extensive experiential will change students' behavior, understanding and thinking. Through various experientials students are more creative in making decisions.

Negotiation Text

Waluyo ^[10] Wahono, ^[11] the text of exemplum is a type of fictitious text containing incidents which the participant / perpetrator does not need to happen or events that can't be avoided.

Khalimah, et al, ^[12] exemplum text is a type of text that describes a human life experiential or character behavior of a story. In text exemplum there is a text structure,

the structure includes orientation, incident, and interpretation.

Mahsun, ^[13] says that the text of exemplum is a text that has a social purpose assessing the behavior or character in the story. That's why this text has structure: title, introduction / orientation, event / incident and interpretation.

MATERIALS & METHODS

This research was conducted at SMP Muhammadiyah 57 Medan which is on Mustafa St, No. 1, Gelugur Darat 1, East Medan District. The research will be conducted in November 2017 until January 2018. The population of this study is all students of class IX SMP Muhammadiyah 57 Medan academic year 2015/2016. Sampling used in this study set all students of class IX SMP Muhammadiyah 57 Medan that is as much as 54 students. For a limited test the study took 30% of the total number of subjects as many as 19 people taken from class IX-1, then continued with all students for a limited trial.

The model that will be developed in this research is one of the learning model of student centered oriented that is experiential learning model, based on research and development model of learning system that is 4-D model, stands for Define, Design, Develop, Disseminate.

Data collection techniques research development of experiential learning model in accordance with the development model used is 4-D Define, Design, Development, and Dissemination. Developed by Thiagrajan (1974). Data collection techniques used in the form of interviews, literature studies, questionnaires, observation sheets, product trial sheets, and documentation.

The instrument used in this study is the instrument given to the learning expert and the design expert of the learning as the model development validator. Instruments are also given to students as objects in this study. Instruments given to the subject matter and the instructional design expert are intended to validate the resulting product

development. This is intended as a fulfillment of the requirements of the developed learning model.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Analysis of Test Result Data

Definition Stage

Analysis of interviews conducted on five teachers and a number of students in class IX SMP Muhammadiyah 57 Medan at the definition stage is as follows:

a. All teachers (3 teachers) are familiar with the experiential learning model whereas all students (17) have not yet understood the experiential learning model. Therefore the researcher explained to the students about the description of the model so that the students get the understanding and the research can be continued for the next step.

- b. b) All teachers (3) have not used an experiential learning model in learning and all students do not understand that teachers have used experiential learning models in learning.
- c. All teachers (100%) do not use experiential learning models and all students do not understand that teachers have used experiential learning models in learning.
- d. All teachers said that it requires the use of experiential learning models and students who respond to the need to use this learning model as many as 10 people (75%).
- e. All teachers are happy with the use of experiential learning models and students are happy with the use of experiential learning models.
- f. Most respondents (85%) say motivated to follow the learning by using experiential learning model.

Design Stage

Table 1. Analysis of Aspects of Learning Design from Colleague

No	Aspect	Total Rating Score	Percentage	Criteria
1	Subject Identity	8	100%	Very Good
2	Formulation of Indicators	17	70,83%	Good
3	Formulation of Learning Objectives	14	87,5%	Good
4	Selection of teaching materials	18	75%	Very Good
5	Selection of learning resources	17	70,83%	Good
6	Selection of learning media	19	79,16%	Very Good
7	Learning Model	13	81,25%	Very Good
8	Learning scenario	22	68,75%	Good
9	Evaluation	27	84,37%	Very Good
Average Criteria			71,76%	Good

In general, out of the nine aspects that have been given to reviewers through questionnaires, the product development design has been very good with average generalized score of 71.76% with a rating range of 55% percentage rating $\leq X \leq 75\%$ with good criteria.

In addition to assessing the design of the lesson, assessment is also conducted for teaching materials in the form of teaching materials used in the development of experiential learning model. Assessment was given by two peer teachers of the field

of study of the Indonesian language to get quality improvement. Based on the data obtained can be said that the assessment obtained from peers to the material of writing text exemplum is very good.

Development Stage

Based on the assessment that has been given to colleagues, the next stage of product development validation. This validation is performed by competent material experts according to their expertise. The selected expert is a lecturer of the

Faculty of Education Technology, which amounts to two people. One validates the instructional design and another validates

the teaching materials given to the students in the learning process.

Table 2. Results Validation Against Aspects of Learning Design

No	Aspect	Score	Percentage	Criteria
1.	Subject Identity	4	100%	Very Good
2.	Formulation of Indicator	10	83,33%	Very Good
3.	Formulation of Learning Objectives	7	87,5%	Very Good
4.	Material Selection	10	83,88%	Very Good
5.	Selection of Learning Resources	11	91,66%	Very Good
6.	Selection of Learning Media	10	83,33%	Very Good
7.	Learning Model	7	87,5%	Very Good
8.	Learning Scenario	12	75%	Very Good
9.	Evaluation	14	87,5%	Very Good
Average Percentage			86,63%	Very Good

Based on the eligibility criteria of the instructional design product, the scores obtained on the validation of the learning design are within the eligible criteria. This criterion indicates that the instructional design product on the resulting development is feasible to be tested in the learning process.

Validation is also given to the material expert to see the material feasibility in accordance with the development of the designed learning model. The results of validation of material experts on aspects of teaching materials obtained criteria worthy. This criterion indicates that the product of learning materials on the resulting development is very feasible to be tested into the learning process.

The effectiveness of product development in this research is seen from the result of questionnaire of learning motivation to students and observation sheet with predefined criteria. In this stage, the trial was conducted in a limited way involving 17 students as respondents.

In addition to seeing the extent to which students' motivation in the application of product development, but can be seen student activities during the learning process took place with ten categories of observation. The ten categories of observation continue to be used as a reference observation of student activity in research. Based on the observation result, the number of students who pay attention to the teacher's explanation of 12

people with percentage 70.58% of the total students in the limited trial. Category of students reading books for 7 people with percentage 41.36%, asking questions as many as 6 people with a percentage of 35.29%, responding to questions (opinion) 8 teachers with a percentage of 47.05%, responding to the question (opinion) 11 students with percentage of 64.70%, exchanging opinions with a group of 6 people with percentage of 35.29% percent, expressing idea clearly 13 people with percentage 76,47%, listening explanation student 8 people with percentage 47,055, writing relevant to KBM 4 people with a percentage of 11.76%.

Disseminate Stage

After the development product gets validation from the experts, the product is ready to be tested to the students in the learning process. To see the effectiveness of the developed product, the questionnaire distributed learning motivation to students and peer-reviewed sheets by filling out the list of available observation categories. Questionnaires containing statements are arranged in twenty items and responses vary widely from students.

The result of the analysis to the questionnaire of student's learning motivation with the development of experiential learning model obtained total score of 3474 with maximum score 4320 percentage of score is 80.39%. If the number

is converted against the predetermined criteria and is within the range of 75% $\leq X \leq 100\%$ percent is included in the very good criterion.

Learning to write text exemplum by using experiential learning model. Aspects of observation are obtained before, arranged in twelve activities of the students. Analyzes of observed results in an expanded trial are; (a) Based on the observations made on the students' activities during the learning process, 46 students observed the teacher explanation, 32 students did the activity of reading the book, 35 people asked questions when the learning took place. 34 students responded to teachers' comments, 24 responded to other students' opinions, 45 exchanged opinions with group mates, 23 expressed ideas clearly, 23 people wrote things relevant to the learning process, and 6 students did activities that did not relevant to the learning process; (b) The description of student activity during learning with the development of experiential learning model is good. The categories of positive observations are filled with good. This is an indication that students are generally motivated in following the learning activities with the development of experiential learning model, especially text exemplum.

CONCLUSION

The validation result from the learning design expert on the product of the development of this experiential learning model shows that the quality of the designed instructional design product is very good; The validation result from the learning material expert on the teaching materials contained in the product development indicates that the learning material contained in the development product has been very good; Students' responses based on learning motivation and observation of student activity in the expanded trial stage found the very good criteria; Based on the total percentage score of student activity in the expanded trial stage obtained the percentage of the total score of 88.16%, if the questionnaire is converted against

predetermined assessment criteria and based on the 75% score range $\leq X \leq 100\%$ the percentage is included in the very good criteria

REFERENCES

1. Ministry of Education and Culture of the Republic of Indonesia. Bahasa Indonesia Wahana Pengetahuan. (Jakarta: Center of Curriculum, 2015).
2. Anis. Improving Student Learning Outcomes In Writing Exemplum Text with Jigsaw Learning Method. (Tanjung Siang: MPD, 2017).
3. Atikah. Development of Project Based Learning Model Through Contextual Approach in Writing Text of News, __: __, Vol. __, 2015.
4. Ni Kadek, et al. Relationship Motivation Student Learning with Ability to Write Text Exemplum Class IX SMP Negeri 1 Singaraja. (Singaraja: Ganesha Education University, 2017).
5. Mutmainnah. Development of Mathematical Learning Model Based on Pepro Creation at Madrasah Tsanawiyah. (Jakarta: Jakarta State University, 2016).
6. Musdalifah Amir, et al. Development of Learning-Based Learning Tools on Students Class XI IPA SMA Negeri 9 Blonde. (Jurnal Sains dan Pendidikan Fisika (JSPF), Sulawesi Selatan, 2015).
7. Silberman, Mel. Handbook of Experiential Learning. (Bandung: Nusa Media: 2014).
8. Sanjaya, Wina. Education: Types, Methods and Procedures. (Jakarta: Kencana, 2014).
9. Sani, Ridwan Abdullah. Learning Innovation. (Jakarta: Bumu Aksara, 2014).
10. Waluyo, Budi. Indonesian Language and Literature for Class IX and MTS. (Solo: PT. Tiga Serangkai, 2015)

11. Wahono, et al. Proficient in Indonesian. (Jakarta: Erlangga, 2016).
12. Khalimah, et al. Master's Ability in Preparation of Evaluation for Text Lessons 2013 Classroom Students IX in SMPN 1 Bandar. (Singaraja: Ganesha Education University, 2016).
13. Mahsun. Text in Indonesian Language Learning Curriculum 2013. (Jakarta: PT. Raja Grafindo Persada, 2014)

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